

Effects of Computer Animation Instructional Package (CAIP) on Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Geometry in Oyo Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria

Kamoru Abiodun Sabitu ✉

*Department of Science Education, School of General Studies Education,
Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo, Nigeria*

Saddiq Khalid

*Department of Mathematics, School of Secondary Education (Science Programmes),
Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo, Nigeria*

Abstract

This study investigated effects of Computer Animation Instructional Package (CAIP) Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Geometry in Oyo Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. The researchers employed quasi-experimental design of the pretest, posttest, non-randomized and non-equivalent control group design. Purposive sampling technique was used to select one hundred and eighty four (184) senior secondary school students Oyo metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. The experimental group was exposed to computer animation instructional package while the control group was taught geometry using conventional approach. The instrument used for data collection was Geometry Achievement Test (GAT) and two lesson plans with reliability co-efficient of 0.89. The data collected were analysed using mean, standard deviation and t-test statistics. The result of the study revealed that there was a significant difference in the performance of students taught geometry using computer animation and the control, $t_{(117)}=7.34, P<$. Also, gender has no influence on students' performance in geometry, $t_{(66)}= 0.69, P> 0.05$. The study recommended among others that Stakeholders in education and professional bodies should train and retrain teachers on how to use instructional games such as computer animation instructional package for teaching geometry concepts and mathematics as a subject.

Keywords: *Computer Animation Instructional Package, Students' Academic Achievement, Geometry and Nigeria*

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Introduction

The cornerstone of science and technology is mathematics. Arithmetic, algebra, trigonometry, geometry, and other branches make up this abstract science of numbers, quantity, and space. It is researched as an abstract idea or as it relates to other fields like engineering and physics. The study of mathematics encompasses many different topics, some of which deal with abstract ideas that are difficult to connect to real-world situations. To guarantee that students fully comprehend these abstract ideas, teachers must provide a clear explanation and step-by-step guidance. Like all academic subjects, mathematics is founded on fundamental laws and principles. As such, students who have a poor understanding of these concepts may find it challenging to understand the subject matter (Mohammed & Luka, 2019). It has been said that mathematics is a precise tool that everyone uses to have a clear comprehension of the physical universe. It plays a significant and distinctive role in human communities and is strategically important to maintaining the advancement of all people (Sabitu, 2023).

Even though mathematics is important, secondary school pupils' performance in the subject is concerning. Researchers have identified several significant factors that contribute to students' mathematical failure, such as family background, peer group, lack of practice, students' poor mathematical background, parental influence on career choice, poor pedagogical approach or strategies, students' lack of participation in hands-on classroom activities, teachers' incompetence in teaching challenging math concepts, students' poor study habits, and teachers' failure to connect mathematical concepts to real-world activities (Salman, Mohammed, Ogundele, & Ayinla, 2022).

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Due to the previously listed elements that impact mathematics learning, researchers have been conducting studies to determine how to integrate ICT in the classroom as an adjunct to traditional teaching methods to improve students' mathematical performance. Computer technologies like Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI), Mobile Learning Application (MLA), Simulation, and Computer Animation Instructional Package (CAIP), to name a few, are the result of alternate methods of teaching mathematics.

To put it simply, computer animation is the process of giving inanimate objects alive on a screen. Animators create characters that are larger than life and lifelike. ICT-based computer animation is a teaching and learning strategy that has been shown to help students grasp challenging concepts. The researchers found that teaching via computer animation is a more successful method of instruction. Computer animation is an electronic tool or teaching object that uses a machine to create moving objects with various attributes (images, forms, etc.) to represent actions, reactions, skill outcomes, and learning outcomes.

Computer animations, according to Bamidele and Yoade (2017), may increase the likelihood that students would learn more, remember information better, and even perform better when it comes to the abilities they are meant to acquire. There are two

types of animation: 2D and 3D, and the goal of both is to raise students' mathematical achievement. In their 2020 study, Musa, Ziatdinov, and Griffiths explore the significance of animation—basically, a type of pictorial presentation that has emerged as the key component of technology-based learning environments. According to research, educational computer animation has emerged as one of the most sophisticated methods for providing multimedia content to students, and its importance in aiding comprehension and memory of information has grown significantly with the introduction of potent graphics-oriented computers.

A study conducted in 2021 by Gambari, Falode, and Adegbenro investigated the impact of computer animation and geometry instructional model on junior secondary school students' retention and achievement in mathematics. The findings demonstrated that pupils who were taught geometry by animation outperformed their peers who were taught the subject through traditional means. Academic achievement is a significant component that is impacted by the way that students are taught (Aasa & Sabitu, 2023). The act of accomplishing something, especially with skill and effort, is called achievement. Academic achievement, then, is the fulfilment of one's academic aims, one's educational results, or, more accurately, the degree to which one has met one's stated educational goals as a student, teacher, or instructor.

One of the mathematics subjects that students struggle with is geometry. The study of the measurement, relationships, and characteristics of points, lines, angles, and figures in space is known as geometry (Houghton, 2015). The foundation of engineering and technical advancement is geometry. In mathematics, achievement is defined as a performance that can be quantified through scores. It is the capacity to hold onto and then recall what one has encountered or learnt within a certain period. Students' academic accomplishments, which highlight their mathematical knowledge, comprehension, and application levels, are indicative of a quality mathematics education. Exams or ongoing assessments can be used to gauge students' proficiency in geometry. Aremu and Sokan (2021) contend that secondary education serves as the foundation for higher education and that problems are likely to arise at higher levels if a weak foundation is established.

Numerous researchers have taken gender into account when studying mathematics. Male or female identity is referred to as one's gender (usually referring to Social and Cultural differences rather than biological ones). Gender is therefore a social or cultural variable that differs between societies or locales. Teachers have been interested in and concerned about the topic of gender and performance. The coeducational nature of the schools in the research makes gender a critical problem in modern times. Furthermore, gender-related discrepancies in academic achievement have made it necessary to confirm how animation-based instructional packages can affect students' mathematical abilities. More research that takes gender into account is, therefore, necessary to create fresh information regarding the impact of computer animation education packages on geometry students' academic performance.

Review of Related Literatures

The Dual Coding Theory of Visualization serves as the foundation for this study's theoretical framework. Theoretically, words and exterior images activate the coding system in an additive manner, according to the dual coding theory (Paivio, 1986). Furthermore, there is a higher chance of retrieval when data is dual-coded. Furthermore, according to dual coding theory, words and images trigger different parts of the brain. Dual coding theory has been widely used to guide studies using computer-

generated static or animated displays in computer-based, multimedia learning environments (Mayer & Anderson, 1992; Mayer & Sims, 1994). Students will therefore be able to better utilize their ability to process information on two levels by stimulating the visual system and lessening the strain on the verbal processing system, which will improve performance, when they are exposed to genetics through computers through texts and diagrams. This notion served as the foundation for our investigation.

Due to the lack of resources in the early days of computers, there hasn't been much work done in Nigeria on the design and research of animation (Onansanya, Shehu, Iwokwagh, & Soetan, 2010). Thankfully, animation is now easier to make because to the availability of low-cost, user-friendly software. Examples of these software programs are Cinema 4D and the Macromedia Creative Suite. These are computer programs that can be used to create visuals and even animation three-dimensional processes. As a result, animation has been created for educational purposes and has yielded many positive outcomes. Studies on the integration of animation have demonstrated beneficial effects on learning, including a decrease in the cognitive load that students experience when completing learning tasks; the potential for increased learning when content requires motion and external visualization; and chances for the classification of complex information (Akpınar & Ergin 2008; Dancy & Beichner, 2006; Dasdemir et al., 2008; Iskander, 2005, Li, Santhanam, & Carswell, 2009; Onansanya et al., 2010; Rieber, 1994; Rieber & Boyce, 1990). Park (1998) drew conclusions regarding the impact of animations, citing a number of empirical studies that showed how they may be used to explain complicated phenomena, communicate domain knowledge about dynamic processes, and draw attention to specific areas of interest. More effectively than text or static pictures, animation may convey dynamic, complicated sequences of biological phenomena, as noted by Stith (2004), McClean et al. (2005), and O'Day (2006). By encouraging the development of dynamic mental representations of the topic under study, the use of animations may help improve conceptual understanding (Akpınar & Ergin 2008).

Computer animation is a useful tool for teaching biology issues in particular because of its unique qualities, the complexity of the systems involved in biology generally, and the spatial and transient nature of many biological processes.

Additionally, it's possible that using static images alone won't be all that effective. A sizable body of research suggests that animations, as opposed to static sequential images, are a more effective teaching tool for dynamic events (Pollock et al., 2002; Poohkay 1994; Tversky & Morrison, 2002). Results of a study by Rieber and Boyce (1990) comparing animation-based training with meticulously planned verbal presentations reveal that while the animation did not increase the amount of information taught, it did reduce the amount of time needed to retrieve the knowledge.

However, it has been discovered that the best animations occur when text is spoken concurrently with significant structures to support the learning process (O'Day, 2006; Ustuner & Sancar, 1999). After a thorough analysis of the literature spanning all academic fields, the second study came to this conclusion. The contiguity effect is a common name for this phenomenon. Additionally, research indicates that for animations to be effective, students could want assistance paying attention to the pertinent portions of the animation (Mayer & Anderson, 1992). In other words, they might require training in the use of animations. Nevertheless, it is still unclear whether or not utilizing animation in instructions may help students learn more, even though it appears to grab their attention and boost their enthusiasm to learn. With so many

resources at their disposal, academics may conduct further research on the usefulness of animations in life science education.

Several researches have suggested that when computers are utilized for instruction, gender may play a role. It's a common belief that boys stand to gain more from the incorporation of technology into teaching and learning since they are more inclined to use it. Conversely, girls might not be able to learn as much when it comes to technology. This study's investigation of gender may assist to make these problems more clear.

Gender concerns in education also touch on a wide range of other topics. These include how differently men and women perceive visual information, how differently they learn science through computer-based learning resources, how differently they perform academically in science classes, how differently they view and feel about computers, and how anxious they are to use them. (Madell & Muncer, 2004; Wong & Hanafi, 2007; Aremu, 2008; Butler, 2000; Enochsson, 2005; Isman & Celikli, 2009). Therefore, it would be advantageous to look into whether the gender of the students using the animations will affect their academic performance.

Statement of the Problem

Students consistently do poorly on internal and external exams in geometry, the foundational subject of engineering and technological advancement. It has been noted that applicants perform poorly in 3D and circular geometry questions because they are weak in these areas. The basic, conventional teaching approach that is being utilized in our secondary schools to teach geometry has come under fire and has been called teacher-centred. Numerous factors have been linked to this low performance, such as teachers' lack of subject-matter expertise, their poor teaching strategies, the absence of teaching resources, students' misconceptions and misinterpretations of the questions, and their failure to embrace the endless potential of technology.

To solve this issue and get pupils actively involved in the teaching and learning process, it is necessary to look for an interactive approach. Thus, the utilization of computer animation instructional packages is the technique taken into consideration in this study. The purpose of this study was to determine how an animated instructional package affected the academic achievement of senior secondary school geometry students, and to improve the students' subpar performance by minimizing theoretical exposition and making use of it.

Purpose of Study

This study's primary goal was to ascertain the effects of Computer Animation Instructional Package (CAIP) Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Geometry in Oyo Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study were to ascertain:

1. The impact of the Computer Animation Instructional Package (CAIP) on senior secondary school students' academic performance in geometry.
2. The impact of gender on senior secondary school students' academic progress in geometry through the use of the Computer Animation Instructional Package (CAIP).

Research Questions

Throughout this investigation, the following research questions were addressed:

1. How does the Computer Animation Instructional Package (CAIP) affect senior secondary school pupils' academic performance in geometry?
2. Does the academic performance of male and female students who use computer animation teaching packages differ in any way?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of senior secondary school students taught geometry with computer animation instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional approach.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students taught geometry using a computer animation instructional package.

Materials and Methods

The quasi-experimental design was used in this investigation. In particular, the non-equivalent control group design with pretest and posttest was applied. Since intact courses were utilized to prevent disruptions to regular class instruction, a quasi-experimental design is deemed appropriate for this particular investigation. This study's population consists of Senior Secondary School 2 students in 34 public secondary schools in the four local government Areas of in Oyo Town, Oyo State, Nigeria. These are Afijio, Atiba, Oyo East, and Oyo West local governments. The class was considered because the students in SSS 2 are no longer transiting into the senior school as in the case of SSS 1 students, and neither are they preparing for external examinations as in the case of SSS 3 students. They are more stable in the senior class than in the other two classes. Two schools were chosen for the study using a purposeful random sampling technique. The study involved one hundred and eighty-four (184) senior high school pupils. Ninety-seven (97) students—43 males and 54 females—were part of the experimental group, which used a computer animation instructional package to teach, while eight seven (87) students—38 males and 49 females—belonged to the control group, which used a conventional technique. The experimental and control groups were randomly assigned to the students. While the control group used a traditional teaching style, the experimental group used computer animation as their educational tactic.

The Geometry Achievement Test (GAT) was the tool used to collect the data. The geometry principles were also taught using two lesson plans. The GAT is divided into two sections: part A contains student information, and section B has thirty (30) multiple-choice questions based on the four geometry themes that are taught—two-dimensional shapes, three-dimensional shapes, angles, and construction of angles. Experts in mathematics education, measurement, and evaluation from the Department of Science Education at the University of Ibadan approved the instrument's face and content. The test items that were included in the instrument's final draft were reorganized based on their feedback. The Kuder-Richardson (K-R20) formula was utilized by the researchers to conduct a reliability investigation on GAT. The estimate of dependability was 0.89. The six-week data collection process involved giving the experimental group only computer animation and traditional teaching methods to explain the geometry topic, while the control group received the GAT as a pre-test. Only the traditional method of instruction was used with the control groups.

Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to the acquired data for analysis. The t-test statistics were used to assess the hypotheses at the 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Results

The results were arranged according to the stated research questions and hypotheses as follows:

Answer to Research Questions

Research Question 1: What is the effect of Computer Animation Instructional Package (CAIP) on students' academic achievement in Geometry in senior secondary school?

Table 1. Mean Gain Score of Students' Academic Achievement for both Experimental and Control Groups

Group	Number	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental (Comp. Animation)	97	24.56	8.90	38.18	8.36	13.62
Control (conventional method)	87	24.54	6.78	25.53	7.05	0.99

The mean gain score of the students who took the geometry performance test is displayed in Table 1: Students who were exposed to computer animation had a mean gain score of 13.62, whereas students who were traditionally taught geometry had a mean gain score of 0.99. The experimental group's gain score was 12.63 points greater than the control group. Research hypothesis one was derived from additional analysis done to see if the mean difference was statistically significant.

Research Question 2: Is there any difference in the academic achievement of male and female students exposed to computer animation instructional packages?

Table 2. Mean Gain Score of Male and Female Students Taught Geometry Using Computation Animation Instructional Package

Group	Number	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Male	43	24.36	9.10	35.45	9.64	11.09
Female	54	24.74	8.70	36.86	7.02	12.12

The mean gain score of the group of male and female students exposed to the computer animation instructional package is displayed in Table 2. Male students exposed to computer animation had an average gain score of 11.09, whereas female students exposed to computer animation had an average gain score of 12.12. The female students' primary gain score was greater than the male students'. Research hypothesis two was derived from additional analysis done to see if the mean difference was statistically significant.

Test of Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of senior secondary school students when taught using computer animation and when using conventional method.

Table 3. T-Test Analysis of the Academic Performance of Students Exposed to Computer Animation and Those Taught Geometry Using Conventional Method

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value
Experimental	97	38.18	8.36	184	7.34	.000*
Control	87	25.53	7.05			

Note: P<0.05, **significant

The t-test analysis of the pupils' performance is displayed in Table 3. According to the table, the null hypothesis was rejected since $t(117)=7.34$, $p = 0.00$, which is less than the significance level (0.05). As a result, pupils who learn geometry via computer-based instruction perform far better academically than those who learn those using traditional methods.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught geometry using the computer animation instructional package.

Table 4. T-Test of Male and Female Taught Geometry Using Computer Animation Instructional Package

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value
Male	38	35.45	9.64	85	0.69	0.493
Female	49	36.86	7.02			

Note: P<0.05, Not significant

The t-test analysis of the performance of male and female students is displayed in Table 4. According to the table, $t(66)= 0.69$, $p = 0.493$. Since the p-value is higher than the significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis was accepted, suggesting that there may not be a significant difference between male and female students' academic performance when teaching geometry using a computer animation instructional package.

Discussion

The impact of computer animation instructional packages and traditional teaching methods on the academic performance of senior secondary school pupils was compared in this study. Its goal was to determine whether geometry students taught using a computer animation instructional package outperformed those taught using a more traditional method. According to the study, students who were taught geometry via computer animation performed far better academically than those who were taught geometry using a traditional method. Students who received geometry training through

a computer animation instructional program outperformed those who received instruction through a more traditional means. This finding is consistent with the findings of Adeniyi and Salman (2016), who claimed that employing computer animation training packages to teach geometry improved students' academic performance.

In addition, although the female students performed somewhat better than the male students, this study demonstrated no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students taught geometry utilizing a computer animation instruction package. A recent study by Sabitu (2023) that analyzed the mathematical performance of men and women revealed that there is no discernible difference in gender when it comes to the use of instructional packages and the teaching and learning of mathematics.

Conclusion

The study concluded and recommended that:

- Math teachers should be encouraged to use computer animation training packages to teach mathematical concepts.
- Professional associations such as the Science Teachers Association, the Mathematical Association of Nigeria, and other education stakeholders ought to periodically arrange seminars and workshops for math teachers that focus on the efficient use of computer animation instruction packages in the teaching of geometric concepts.

When teaching geometry ideas through computer animation instruction packages, math teachers should be mindful of gender concerns.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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